

Common Regional Market

September 2023

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context and progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find a first outline of the baseline data collected during 2022 and the first months of 2023.

In terms of Common Regional Market, the monitoring focuses, on the one hand, on the context indicator “Knowledge-intensive service exports” and, on the other hand, on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see on the backside of this document).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Knowledge-intensive service exports (in percent)

Knowledge-intensive service exports refer to the international trade of services that – such as professional, scientific and technical services – rely heavily on specialised knowledge and expertise. These services are typically provided by highly skilled professionals and are characterised by a high degree of customisation, innovation and knowledge intensity.

Source

Authors’ calculation based on EC (2022)
<https://tinyurl.com/sourcecalculations>

Note

Knowledge-intensive service exports are given as share of total value of services exports.

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Priority

Regional Indicators

Strengthening regional economic cooperation
and the Common Regional Market

<p>Tool Kit for Skills for supporting Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3)</p>	<p>Analysis of Value Chains in the WB Economies</p>	<p>S3 Implementation Framework</p>
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Legend: On track or maintaining achievement

Moderately improving, Challenges remain

Stagnating, Significant challenges

Decreasing, Major challenges

Information not available

WB Economy Indicators

Performance of the WB economy: good medium to be improved information not provided

	Prepared S3 and their implementation supported					Increased investment in SMEs			Linking Western Balkan education and innovation activities				
	S3 milestones	Local S3 support	S3 dialogue	EU & sector support	Peer exchange (events, docs)	Access to Finance (AF) perception	Macro-regional strategies	WB in EEN & EYE	WB in COST & EUREKA	IPR support	Innovation agency collaboration	Infrastructure support	
AL	Not yet	Workshop organised, publications prepared	Meetings held	Meetings held	Event organised, publications prepared	Moderate obstacle	Participation in several programmes	EEN, EYE participation, visibility, pool of beneficiaries	Active participation & promotion of COST	Numerous events, information on publications not provided	Mous and joint initiatives in place	Facility in place, limited number of projects	
BIH	Not yet	Workshop organised, Publications not specified	Information not provided	Information not provided	Event organised, info on participants, publications not provided	Moderate obstacle	Participation in several programmes	EEN, EYE participation, visibility, pool of beneficiaries	Active participation & promotion of COST	Numerous events, large number of participants	Not applicable	Several facilities supporting number of projects	
XK*	Not yet	Workshops organised, Publications not specified	Information not provided	Information not provided	Events organised, info on participants, publications not provided	Moderate obstacle	No participation	EEN participation, visibility	Active participation & promotion of COST	Numerous events, publications, information on participants not provided	Not applicable	Few facilities supporting number of projects with considerable funding	
MNE	In place	Workshops organised, publication prepared	Meetings held	Meetings held	Event organised, publication prepared	Moderate obstacle	Participation in several programmes	EEN, EYE participation, visibility	Active participation & promotion of COST	Information not provided	Information not provided	Information not provided	
MK	Not yet	Workshops organised, publication prepared	No meetings held	No meetings held	No events, no publications	Moderate obstacle	Participation in several programmes	EEN, EYE participation, visibility, pool of beneficiaries	Active participation & promotion of COST	Numerous events, publications, information on participants not provided	Mous not signed, joint initiative in place	Few supported projects with considerable funding	
RS	In place	Workshops organised, publication prepared	Information not provided	Information not provided	Information not provided	Moderate obstacle	Participation in several programmes	EEN, EYE participation, visibility, pool of beneficiaries	Active participation in COST	Numerous publications, events with specified participation	Info on Mous not provided	Several facilities supporting number of projects	

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